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MONITORING OF THE COASTAL AND SHELF ZONE OF THE BLACK SEA IN 2020, GEORGIA

Abstract. Research paper deals with the ecological condition of the Georgian Black Sea coastal zone. Evaluation of water quality is the necessary component of any research and only through such evaluation it is possible to create comprehensive picture about the water eco-system. For the estimation of ecological condition of the Georgian Black Sea coastal line considered the results of investigations of 4 monitoring stations and 9 stations which covers the almost whole Georgian Black Sea coast including 2 transects (Gonio, Poti). The monitored area included the shelf zone of the Georgian Black Sea waters from the Turkish border to the Enguri River delta. In addition, sampling and analyses were done in the main rivers in the Black Sea Region in Georgia – Rioni, Kodori, Inguri, Chorokhi.

Keywords: water, heavy metals, contamination, concentration, pollution quality

Introduction

The Black Sea is an area of both ecological and economic importance. Its coast possesses a unique recreational potential. The sea includes a zone of heightening biological productivity also provides a spawning, wintering and inhabit areas for many valuable fish species. As a result, the Black Sea is among the most remarkable regional seas globally and one of the most important natural formations for the country's general geographical location because of its resource potential and recreational area. Georgia accounts for 9% of the length of the Black Sea coast. Besides, it has a significant influence on the pattern of the Georgian climate. 90% of the Sea is naturally anoxic, however, the top 150m of water column represents an area of great biological productivity.

Evaluation of the existing qualitative condition of the Black Sea environment is necessary to define the target state indicators and plan specific measures to achieve the target situation. The Black Sea Monitoring Program is an obligation defined by the EU-Georgia Association Agreement. In particular, in accordance with the EU Marine Strategy Framework, Georgia is obliged to create a monitoring program and carry out constant monitoring according to the parameters established for the assessment of the Black Sea Environmental Status, which includes physical, chemical, biological parameters.

Materials and Methods

Study of ecological condition of coastal zone has high importance for the evaluation of level and nature of anthropogenic impact on the sea ecosystem. Evaluation of water quality is

the necessary component of any research and only through such evaluation, it is possible to create comprehensive picture about the water eco-system [1].

For the estimation of ecological condition of the Georgian Black Sea coastal zone considered investigation of 4 stations located on coastal line of Adjara. The stations Sarpi and Green cape were selected as reference water areas, being relatively less anthropogenically influenced. Batumi and Batumi Harbor were selected as having more intense anthropogenic pressure from household and industry. The observation scheme is provided in table 1.

Table 1. Monitoring Scheme for Georgian Coastal Line

Station №	Station	Station coordinates		Observation depths, m
		Longitude	Latitude	
1	Sarpi	41.543261°	41.557807°	surface
2	Pier Batumi	41.656571°	41.633083°	surface
3	Batumi Port	41.650911°	41.644562°	surface
4	Green Cape	41.691792°	41.703510°	surface

Monitored parameters were temperature, salinity, turbidity, conductivity, pH, ORP, suspended solids, dissolved oxygen, BOD₅, nutrients – ammonia, nitrite, nitrate, phosphate and silicate, heavy metals, TPH [2].

Using the horizontal type bathometer sea water samples were taken at surface. Determination of dissolved oxygen based on the Iodometric method of the International Standardization Organization – ISO 5813:1983. Estimation of dissolved oxygen in the sea water was carried out with Winkler titration method by the TITREX burette. Salinity and temperature were detected by electrometric method (STC-2K, Toho Dentan Co. Ltd); pH – Electrochemical method (Equipment – MIWAUKEE KRK KP-10Z).

Total suspended solids were determined according to Glass fibre filtration method EN 872:200 (Water quality. Determination of suspended solids; membrane 0.4 µm Polycarbonate (Hydrophilic) diam.: 47 mm filters). After the preliminary processing the contents of nutrients – ammonia, nitrites, nitrates, phosphates, silicates – in the water samples were estimated by the continuous flow analyzer – SKALAR SAN^{plus} ANALYZER (see Figure 2). The functioning of the

device is based on standard methods for nutrient identification. Preliminary treatment considered sample filtration (Glass Microfibre Filter GF5 grade, retention 0.7 μm) using All-Glass Vacuum Filter Holder – Sartorius 16309. The above nutrient analysis method allows analysis of large number of samples with the computerized control and calculation of results, with high preciseness ($<0.1\mu\text{mol/l}$) and high sensitivity [3].

For determination of soluble nutrients in the samples prior to the analysis, the samples were filtered in order to eradicate analytical impact of particulate matter. Moreover, the filtration was made for other purpose too – for exclusion of adsorption of nutrients soluble in water by particulate matters. After the sample filtration, the samples were analyzed. The procedure is developed by Kirkwood (1996).

The automated procedure for the determination of Phosphate is based on the following reaction; ammonium heptamolybdate and potassium antimony(II) oxide tartrate react in an acidic medium with diluted solutions of phosphate to form an antimony-phospho-molybdate complex. This complex is reduced to an intensely blue-colored complex by L(+)-ascorbic acid. The complex is measured at 880 nm.

The automated procedure for the determination of Silicate is based on the following reaction; the sample as acidified and mixed with an ammonium heptamolybdate solution forming molybdosilicic acid. This acid is reduced with ascorbic acid to a blue dye, which is measured at 810 nm. Oxalic acid is added to avoid phosphate interference (method according to CEFAS).

The automated procedure for the determination of Nitrite is based on the following reaction; the diazonium compound formed by diazotizing of sulfanilamide by nitrite in water under acid conditions is couple with N-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride to produce a reddish-purple color which is measured at 540 nm (method according to CEFAS) [4–7].

The automated procedure for the determination of Nitrate and Nitrite is based on the cadmium reduction method; the sample is buffered at pH 8.2 and passed through a column containing granulated copper-cadmium to reduce the nitrate to nitrite. The nitrite (originally present plus reduced nitrate) is determined by diazotizing of sulfanilamide and coupling with N-(1-naphthyl) ethylenediamine dihydrochloride to form a highly colored azo dye, which is measured at 540 nm (method according to CEFAS).

The automated procedure for the determination of Ammonia is based on the modified Berthelot reaction; ammonia is chlorinated to monochloramine which reacts with phenol. After oxidation and oxidative coupling a green colored complex is formed. The reaction is catalyzed by nitroprusside; sodium dichloroisocyanurate is used for chlorine donation. The absorption of the formed complex is measured at 630 nm (method according to CEFAS).

Laboratory use water purification system SARTORIUS, arium comfort II ASTM International D1193-06(2018) Standard Specification for Reagent Water type 1.

Black Sea monitoring was conducted by the Environmental Pollution Monitoring Department's Ambient Air, Water and Soil Analyses laboratory Batumi Laboratory of the National Environmental Agency of the Ministry of Environment Protection and Agriculture of Georgia [8].

Results

The monitoring results are presented in the table 2.

Table 2. Monitoring results of Adjara Coastal Line

Sampling Data	Turbidity, NTU	Salinity, ‰	T, °C	Conductivity mS/cm	pH	ORP	Suspended solids, mg/l	Dissolved Oxygen, mg/l	Oxygen saturation, %	BOD5, mg/l
Station – Sarpi										
21.01.2020	2.26	16.6	11.6	28.46	8.03	-87	4.4	9.60	98	1.46
27.02.2020	0.64	16.5	11.0	28.28	8.09	-87	2.8	10.51	106	1.87
12.03.2020	3.78	16.0	11.1	29.03	8.20	-68	10.4	10.16	102	1.77
29.05.2020	2.48	15.5	19.0	26.62	7.98	-85	4.8	8.99	107	2.31
26.06.2020	2.91	16.0	24.6	27.37	7.94	-90	6.0	8.66	115	1.61
31.07.2020	2.47	15.2	27.5	26.18	8.00	-93	5.6	7.80	108	2.88
26.08.2020	3.07	16.0	26.9	27.60	7.92	-89	4.8	7.31	101	2.21
30.09.2020	1.64	18.5	25.7	31.75	8.01	-97	4.4	7.32	101	1.63
26.10.2020	1.69	17.9	21.9	30.31	7.82	-89	2.8	8.50	108	1.89
30.11.2020	0.92	18.5	16.1	31.26	8.20	-104	4.0	8.69	98	1.35
22.12.2020	3.91	16.5	14.3	30.40	8.02	-104	4.8	8.83	96	0.25
Station – Pier Batumi										
21.01.2020	2.69	16.7	11.0	28.56	8.03	-85	13.2	9.66	97	1.81
27.02.2020	2.27	16.6	10.7	23.32	8.05	-85	5.6	9.16	92	1.05
12.03.2020	3.69	14.1	11.3	24.71	7.99	-85	7.6	9.97	100	1.12
29.05.2020	6.33	12.0	18.4	21.20	8.00	-87	6.8	9.46	109	1.29
26.06.2020	11.30	15.6	25.3	26.72	7.92	-90	8.4	7.29	88	1.87
31.07.2020	5.98	13.8	26.4	23.91	7.98	-93	8.0	8.42	113	5.60
26.08.2020	4.69	12.7	25.6	22.24	7.96	-92	5.2	7.83	104	1.95
30.09.2020	4.79	18.4	25.7	30.78	7.99	-96	5.2	7.45	102	0.67
26.10.2020	1.77	18.4	22.8	31.20	7.80	-86	6.0	8.98	116	5.54
30.11.2020	0.4	18.2	15.0	30.84	8.06	-96	5.6	8.34	92	1.55
22.12.2020	5.86	13.3	12.9	25.54	8.04	-96	12.8	9.35	96	0.65
Station – Batumi Port										
21.01.2020	1.77	15.1	11.0	25.98	8.01	-86	6.0	9.03	90	2.88
27.02.2020	2.24	15.2	10.5	26.10	8.40	-84	2.4	9.33	92	1.15
12.03.2020	3.92	13.0	23.7	22.70	7.82	-82	3.2	7.04	90	1.74
29.05.2020	2.5	14.0	11.2	24.36	7.96	-83	5.6	9.46	94	1.46
26.06.2020	4.43	10.8	18.8	19.07	7.94	-83	5.2	8.60	99	1.97
31.07.2020	6.26	10.5	24.5	18.66	7.90	-86	6.4	6.82	87	2.54
26.08.2020	3.68	10.7	24.4	19.01	7.87	-85	4.0	6.78	87	2.27
30.09.2020	1.48	14.6	24.0	25.60	7.99	-94	3.2	6.41	84	1.12
26.10.2020	1.63	15.6	22.3	26.48	7.82	-85	4.0	6.81	86	4.20
30.11.2020	2.53	15.1	14.6	26.01	7.91	-88	2.8	8.00	86	1.21
22.12.2020	4.71	13.3	13.2	26.50	7.95	-88	6.8	8.36	87	6.87
Station – Green Cape										
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
21.01.2020	6.29	16.3	10.2	27.79	8.06	-89	14.0	9.91	98	2.16
27.02.2020	1.85	16.1	10.9	27.87	8.02	-85	4.4	9.80	98	1.54
12.03.2020	2.73	12.4	11.7	21.59	7.97	-84	6.8	9.60	96	1.42
29.05.2020	4.95	13.7	19.4	23.81	8.04	-89	6.4	9.38	112	1.77
26.06.2020	7.73	15.6	25.4	26.80	7.95	-90	8.8	7.83	105	1.62
31.07.2020	4.47	15.1	27.0	25.95	8.08	-97	12.8	8.01	110	3.09
26.08.2020	3.86	12.8	24.9	22.51	8.02	-95	6.4	7.68	101	2.35
30.09.2020	1.62	18.6	25.5	31.97	8.07	-99	8.0	7.16	98	1.10

26.10.2020	1.18	19.1	23.3	31.94	7.80	-84	2.8	8.77	115	4.58
30.11.2020	4.9	16.6	13.1	28.33	8.09	-98	6.4	9.39	98	2.67
22.12.2020	6.97	14.3	12.2	26.60	7.98	-98	2.8	9.08	93	1.05

Temperature – The temperature of the water marine ecosystem is an important factor and can give us the information of dissolved oxygen saturation into the water. During the research period, the surface water temperature of Black Sea coastal zone varied within 10.2 °C (st. Green Cape) – 27.5 °C (st. Sarpi). The average temperature on the stations was: Sarpi – 19.1 °C, Pier Batumi – 18.6 °C, Batumi Port – 18.0 °C, Green Cape – 18.5 °C. Distribution of temperature in surface layer at the investigated stations in 2020 are shown on figure (see figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of temperature in surface layer of Adjara region coastal line in 2020.

Salinity. Water salinity is an important factor for marine investigations. The salinity distribution nature is caused by the land water inflows, causing desalination of surface layers and on the other hand by the inflow of heavy waters with high salinity from the in-depth layers. Salinity in Adjara coastal zone as a rule fluctuates between 15–18‰ on average, which is due to the impact of continental runoff, but in a costal line it can be lower. It changes according to seasons and increases along with the increase of depth. During the research period the absolute salinity of coastal line waters at the surface varied between 12.0‰ (st. Pier Batumi) – 19.1‰ (st. Green Cape). the average salinity on the stations were detected: Sarpi – 16.7‰, Pier Batumi – 15.4 ‰, Batumi Port – 13.4 ‰, Green Cape – 15.5 ‰. Distribution of salinity in surface layer at the investigated stations in 2020 are shown on figure (see figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of salinity in surface layer of Adjara region coastal line in 2020.

DO. Dissolvability of oxygen in water depends on hydro-meteorological conditions, temperature and salinity. As for other types of gasses with the temperature, increase the dissolvability of oxygen reduces. Similar relationship is between the salinity and dissolvability of oxygen.

Moreover, actual content of gasses including oxygen is estimated for the intensity of chemical, biological and hydrological (mix, winter vertical circulation and etc.) processes.

Dissolved oxygen in natural waters is generated as a result of absorption process taking place during the contact of natural waters with the air and as a result of photosynthesis process of sea flora. The content of dissolved oxygen in surface waters varies between 0 to 14 mg/l. Dissolved oxygen is characteristic to the water reservoir O_2 regimes and has high importance for the evaluation of ecological condition of hydrosystem. Dissolved oxygen ensures the breezing of hydrobionts. Oxygen is also necessary for self-cleaning of water units, as participates in the bio-chemical oxidation of admixtures of organic genesis.

High concentration of dissolved oxygen indicates to the regular biological processes taking place in the water reservoirs; reduction of DO – on the pollution of hydro system with the biochemically easily oxidized (first of all organic) substances as well as with the substances which directly chemically react with the oxygen with the consideration of various conditions in the water reservoir (temperature, dissolved oxygen concentration, presence of admixtures with catalyzing function).

During the research period, the dissolved oxygen saturation of coastal line waters at the surface varied between 84%–116%. The minimum DO saturation 84% was detected on the Batumi Port aquatory in June. The maximum DO saturation 116% was detected on the Pier Batumi station in October. The average DO saturation on the stations was detected: Sarpi – 103%, Pier Batumi – 101%, Batumi Port – 89%, Green Cape – 102%. Distribution of the dissolved oxygen in surface layer at the investigated stations in 2020 are shown on figure (see figure 3).

Figure 3. Dissolved Oxygen saturation in Georgian coastal line surface waters in 2020

pH. Sea water has alkali reaction and despite the strong processes the pH content varies within the narrow diapason. Only for the coastal zone, where the impact of river waters inflows is high, the wide variation of pH is identified. pH value depends on temperature and pressure factors. In case of their increasing pH reduces. pH in the Black sea Adjara coastal line waters fluctuates between 7.94-8.40. The minimal pH is reported in October at the station Pier Batumi and maximum – in February at the station Batumi Port.

BOD₅. Existence of oxygen dissolved in natural water has essential and diverse importance. Oxygen as strong oxidant plays important sanitary-hygienic role, as supports fast mineralization of organisms. Content of dissolved oxygen and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) are the important characteristics of water. The average results of estimation of BOD₅ obtained during the research are provided the figure 4.

Figure 4. Average BOD₅ in Georgian coastal line surface waters in 2020

Nutrients. Nitrogen admixtures together with phosphorus and silica admixtures belong to biogenic elements of natural waters. They have special importance in the development of life in water reservoirs. Nitrogen and phosphorus is the necessary ingredient component of tissue of all living organisms. Without these elements the development of sea weeds and accordingly the animals is impossible. On the other hand, concentration of nutrients and their dynamics wholly depend on intensity of biochemical and biological processes in the water reservoirs. However, separation of the above group is conditional at some level, as other elements (*Ca*, *Mg*, *K* and etc.) also participate in life processes.

The main sources of phosphorus and nitrogen admixtures in the sea are the mineralization of organic substances and land water inflows. In the process of dying of organisms, the complex organic substances of tissues and cells are permanently disintegrated. Finally, the organic substances are totally mineralized and mineral forms of nitrogen and phosphorus are regenerated. The second source of phosphorus and nitrogen in the water is land water inflow, which is source of organic substances as well as mineral forms of nitrogen and phosphorus.

In the process of evaluation of ecological condition of sea coastal zone the consideration of hydrochemical factor of river inflows existing in the water collection zones has high importance.

Usage of mineral forms of phosphorus and nitrogen is related to the life processes of organisms. During these processes the phosphorus and nitrogen are absorbed mainly in the form of phosphates and nitrates.

With the consideration of the above factors estimation of nutrients – ammonia NH_4^+ , nitrites NO_2^- , nitrates- NO_3^- , phosphates - PO_4^{3-} , silicates - SiO_3^{2-} is an important part of the present research. Nutrient concentration in Georgian coastal line surface waters in 2020 are shown in the figure 5.

Figure 5. Nutrient concentration in Georgian coastal line surface waters in 2020

Silicate. During the research in the Georgian Black Sea coastal zone the significant variation of silicates was observed at surface level: the concentration of silicates in the surface layer varied within 3.61 μmol/L 78.04 μmol/L limits (see Figure 11). The lowest concentration was observed at station Sarpi, the highest – at station Batumi Port (see Table 3).

Figure 6. Silicate concentration in Georgian coastal line surface waters in 2020

Table 3. Silicates monitoring results of Adjara coastal line

	Sarpi	Pier Batumi	Batumi Port	Green Cape
Min.	3.61	4.82	20.84	8.35
Max.	15.19	69.75	78.04	56.83
Ave.	6.55	20.93	46.97	25.32

Heavy metals. Heavy metals are defined as metallic elements that have a relatively high density compared to water. Their multiple domestic, industrial, agricultural and technological applications have led to their wide distribution in the environment; Their toxicity depends on several factors including the dose, route of exposure, and chemical species, as well as the age, gender, genetics, and nutritional status of exposed individuals. Because of their high degree of toxicity, arsenic, cadmium, chromium, lead, and mercury rank among the priority metals that are of public health significance.

Some heavy metals are naturally occurring elements that are found throughout the earth's crust, but most environmental contamination and human exposure result from anthropogenic activities such as mining and smelting operations, industrial production and use, and domestic and agricultural use of metals and metal-containing compounds. Other group of heavy metals are considered as trace elements because of their presence in trace concentrations (ppb range to less than 10ppm) in various environmental matrices. In the table below, are shown concentration of some heavy metals in the Adjara coastal line surface waters in August 2020:

Figure 7. Concentration of some heavy metals in the Adjara coastal line surface waters in August 2020

The concentration of TPH was determined at investigated stations in August 2020. Results of analyses are shown in the Table 4.

Table 4. Results of analyses of TPH in the Adjara coastal line surface waters (August 2020)

Station	TPH, mg/L
Green Cape	0.0425
Batumi Port	0.0938
Pier Batumi	0.0918
Sarpi	0.0127

In 2020 based on EMBLAS PLUS and EUWI+ project conclusions was started monitoring of the Georgian Black Sea coastal zone. Information related the investigations are shown in the table 5.

Table 5. Monitoring Scheme for Georgian Coastal zone

Station №	Station	Maximum Depth on station, m
NPMS_GE_01_20.09.12	Gonio 1	27.0
NPMS_GE_03_20.09.12	Gonio 2	50.0
NPMS_GE_04_20.09.12	Batumi	28.0
NPMS_GE_07_20.09.12	Kobuleti	27.0
NPMS_GE_10_20.09.11	Poti 1	25.0
NPMS_GE_11_20.09.11	Poti 2	37.0
NPMS_GE_12_20.09.11	Poti 3	55.0
NPMS_GE_13_20.09.11	Anaklia 1	18.0
NPMS_GE_16_20.09.14	Chakvi	27.5

For the monitoring of the Georgian Black Sea coastal zone in September 2020 was organized expedition. The monitoring results are presented in the tables below (see Table 6).

In the Poti transect a surface layer average temperature was 26.53°C, salinity – 16.91‰. pH value in water column for station Poti #1-3 varied within 7.97-8.02. The average value of suspended solids for station Poti #1-3 were 6.4, 4.7 and 4.9 mg/L accordingly. During the research the dissolved oxygen saturation of water column at the Poti transect varied between 100%–102% (see table 5).

Table 6. Monitoring results for Poti transect

Station	Sampling Data	Transparency, m	Sampling Depth m	T, °C	Salinity, ‰	Turbidity, NTU	Conductivity mS/cm	pH	Suspended solids, mg/L
Poti 1	11.09.2020	10.0	surface	26.20	16.89				
			0.5	26.62	16.95	0.50	29.37	8.02	6.0
			1	26.62	16.95				
			2	26.63	16.95				
			4	26.62	16.98				
			5	26.60	16.98	0.44	31.65	8.02	4.0
			6	26.59	16.96				
			8	26.58	16.97				
			10	26.52	16.96	1.07	31.26	8.01	6.4
			20	25.41	16.98	0.42	31.49	8.00	5.6
			23	26.14	16.88	6.68	31.46	8.00	10.0
Poti 2	11.09.2020	5.0	surface	26.49	16.90				
			0.5	26.52	16.90	0.4	31.02	7.97	4.8
			1	26.53	16.91				
			2	26.55	16.51				
			4	26.58	16.92				
			5	26.58	16.93	0.35	31.12	7.99	4.4
			6	26.58	16.98				
			8	26.52	16.94				
			10	26.51	16.94	0.71	31.19	8.00	4.4
			15	26.19	16.94				
			20	26.08	16.87	0.60	30.03	7.97	5.6
			35	26.00	16.90	0.39	29.02	7.97	4.4
			Poti 3	11.09.2020	12.0	surface	26.40	16.92	
0.5	26.49	16.92				0.51	31.28	8.00	4.8
1	26.51	16.93							
2	26.52	16.94							
4	26.54	16.96							
5	26.55	16.96				0.51	31.68	7.99	4.4
6	26.54	16.97							
8	26.51	16.98							
10	26.38	16.98				0.76	31.54	7.99	2.8
15	26.19	16.99							
20	26.25	16.86				0.83	31.37	7.98	6.0
40	20.10	16.46				0.82	31.26	7.97	6.4

In the station Anaklia average temperature of surface (surface-5m) layer was 26.56°C, in the station Batumi - 27.16°C. Average salinity in the station Anaklia was 16.30‰, in the station Batumi. pH value in a water column for stations Anaklia and Batumi varied within narrow range 7.97-8.06. The average value of suspended solids for station Anaklia was 6.5 mg/L. In a station Batumi, suspended solids varied between 4.0-6.4 mg/L and only in a prebottom layer was 26.8

mg/L. During the researches the dissolved oxygen saturation of water column at the station Anaklia varied between 101%–104%, at the station Batumi between 91-106% (see table 7).

Table 7. Monitoring results for the stations Anaklia and Batumi

Station	Sampling Data	Transparency, m	Sampling Depth m	T, °C	Salinity, ‰	Turbidity, NTU	Conductivity mS/cm	pH	Suspended solids, mg/L
Anaklia	20.09.2020	5.0	surface	26.82	15.74				
			0.5	26.76	15.76	2.47	28.14	7.98	6.4
			1	26.76	15.76				
			2	26.48	16.66				
			4	26.18	16.92				
			5	26.33	16.93	0.98	29.19	7.97	6.4
			6	26.32	16.94				
			8	26.29	16.97				
			10	26.28	16.97	0.95	31.09	7.98	7.2
			16	26.11	17.02	1.67	29.13	7.98	6.0
Batumi	20.09.2020	7.0	surface	27.26	15.57				
			0.5	27.26	15.52	1.94	28.30	8.06	4.0
			1	27.24	15.59				
			2	27.18	15.79				
			4	27.06	16.00				
			5	26.96	16.13	2.19	27.94	8.06	6.0
			6	26.66	16.19				
			8	26.55	16.47				
			10	23.06	16.56	1.66	29.00	8.05	4.4
			15	24.05	16.69				
			20	24.00	16.96	1.58	29.15	8.02	6.4
26	20.00	16.13	1.58	29.60	7.99	26.8			

In the Gonio transect a surface layer average temperature was 26.55 and 26.62°C for stations Gonio 1 and Gonio 2 accordingly, while salinity were 16.17 and 16.03 ‰. pH value in water column for station Gonio 1 and Gonio 2 varied within 8.05-8.08. The average value of suspended solids for station Gonio 1 and Gonio 2 were 3.7 and 4.6 mg/L accordingly. During the research the dissolved oxygen saturation of water column at the Gonio transect varied between 104% and 103% (see Table 8).

Table 8. Monitoring results for the stations for Gonio transect

Station	Sampling Data	Transparency, m	Sampling Depth m	T, °C	Salinity, ‰	Turbidity, NTU	Conductivity mS/cm	pH	Suspended solids, mg/L
Gonio 1	20.09.2020	10.0	surface	26.43	15.78				
			0.5	26.54	15.76	0.92	27.78	8.08	2.4
			1	26.59	15.80				
			2	26.76	16.30				
			4	26.50	16.63				
			5	26.45	16.72	0.74	28.68	8.06	4.4
			6	26.46	16.80				
			8	26.39	16.85				
			10	26.09	16.90	0.42	29.36	8.07	4.8
			15	25.09	16.94				
			20	25.03	16.97	0.84	29.15	8.06	4.0
25	25.50	16.12	1.86	28.40	8.07	2.8			
Gonio 2	20.09.2020	7.0	surface	26.56	15.54				
			0.5	26.65	15.65	0.99	28.13	8.08	4.4
			1	26.72	15.75				
			2	26.79	16.08				
			4	26.49	16.48				
			5	26.48	16.66	0.63	29.03	8.07	5.2
			6	26.46	16.76				
			8	26.42	16.83				
			10	26.08	16.84	0.46	29.00	8.07	4.4
			15	25.23	16.94				
			20	21.42	16.45	0.55	29.35	8.05	4.8
			40	25.81	16.29	1.05	29.38	8.05	5.2
			48	25.10	15.89	0.84	28.00	8.06	3.6

In the stations Kobuleti and Chakvi average temperature of surface (surface-5m) layer was 27.19°C and 27.06°C accordingly. In surface layer average salinity in the station Kobuleti was 15.99‰, in the station Chakvi 16.03. pH value in a water column for stations Kobuleti were 7.95-8.07, but in a station Chakvi it changed in narrow range and consist 8.06-8.07. The average value of suspended solids for station Kobuleti and Chakvi were 4.6 and 4.4 mg/L accordingly. During the researches the dissolved oxygen saturation of water column at the station Kobuleti varied between 102%–116%, at the station Chakvi between 104-108% (see table 9).

Table 9. Monitoring results for the stations Kobuleti and Chakvi

Station	Sampling Data	Transpa- rency, m	Sampling Depth m	T, °C	Salinity, ‰	Turbidity, NTU	Conductivity mS/cm	pH	Suspended solids, mg/L
Kobuleti	20.09.2020	1.0	surface	27.41	15.16				
			0.5	27.41	16.12	0.75	29.38	7.95	4.4
			1	27.38	16.13				
			2	27.23	16.14				
			4	26.88	16.18				
			5	26.82	16.19	0.57	28.41	8.06	2.8
			6	26.79	16.22				
			8	26.77	16.35				
			10	26.36	16.59	0.80	28.45	8.07	6.0
			15	25.91	16.80				
			20	21.78	16.55	0.73	29.18	8.06	5.2
26	20.35	16.57	1.01	29.04	8.00	4.8			
Chakvi	20.09.2020	6.0	surface	27.15	15.96				
			0.5	27.14	15.98	0.66	28.31	8.06	4.0
			1	27.11	16.01				
			2	27.10	16.04				
			4	26.99	16.06				
			5	26.86	16.10	0.77	28.16	8.06	4.8
			6	26.83	16.11				
			8	26.82	16.15				
			10	26.84	16.20	0.60	28.52	8.06	4.8
			15	26.37	16.71				
			20	27.00	16.01	0.89	27.78	8.06	4.8
25	26.87	16.00	1.03	28.27	8.07	3.6			

Ammonium. During the researches in the Georgian coastal zone station water samples dissolved ammonium was not determined (LOD 0.47 $\mu\text{mol/L}$).

Nitrites. Concentration of nitrites in 42% of samples weren't determined (LOD 0.07 $\mu\text{mol/L}$). Average concentration of nitrites in stations Gonio, Batumi, Kobuleti and Chakvi were 0.26, 0.27, 0.23 and 0.25 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ accordingly. Concentrations of ammonia, nitrites, nitrates, phosphates and silicates in the monitoring stations are shown in the table (see Table 9).

Nitrates. During investigation in 51% of samples nitrates existing weren't detected (LOD 0.09 $\mu\text{mol/L}$). In the stations Poti 1-3, Gonio 1-2 and Anaklia nitrates were detected only in a surface. Vertical distribution of nitrates in stations Chakvi, Batumi, and Kobuleti are shown in the figure (see figure 8).

Figure 8. Vertical distribution of nitrates in stations Chakvi, Batumi, and kobuleti stations

Silicates. Poti zone is under fresh water low pressure that is why concentration of silicates is relative low than in other zones. In the Poti zone vertical distribution of silicates also was a different, than in other stations.

Table 10. Concentrations of phosphates, nitrites, nitrates, ammonia and silicates in the monitoring stations

Station	Sampling Depth, m	PO ₄ , μmol/L	NH ₄ , μmol/L	NO ₂ , μmol/L	NO ₃ , μmol/L	Si, μmol/L
Anaklia 1	0.5	0.44	<0.47	<0.07	0.10	7.31
	5	0.39	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	1.12
	10	0.30	<0.47	<0.07	0.20	2.36
	16	0.46	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.80
Poti 1	0.5	0.38	<0.47	<0.07	0.73	2.15
	5	0.15	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.60
	10	0.19	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	1.57
	20	0.37	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.70
	23	0.39	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.36
Poti 2	0.5	0.47	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	1.02
	5	0.52	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.38
	10	0.85	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.63
	20	1.17	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.28
	35	0.53	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.20
Poti 3	0.5	0.47	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.44
	5	0.51	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.19
	10	0.49	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.60
	20	0.70	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	0.22
	40	0.32	<0.47	<0.07	<0.09	1.61
Kobuleti	0.5	0.13	<0.47	0.27	0.32	8.01
	5	0.13	<0.47	0.21	0.17	7.10
	10	0.12	<0.47	0.20	<0.09	2.94
	20	0.11	<0.47	0.25	0.30	8.59
	26	0.13	<0.47	0.20	0.17	2.66
Chakvi	0.5	0.14	<0.47	0.27	0.46	9.10
	5	0.12	<0.47	0.21	0.28	9.89
	10	0.11	<0.47	0.23	0.19	8.05
	20	0.10	<0.47	0.29	0.42	9.39
	25	0.12	<0.47	0.25	0.13	9.01
Batumi	0.5	0.13	<0.47	0.24	0.38	14.62
	5	0.13	<0.47	0.24	0.10	10.15
	10	0.12	<0.47	0.24	0.09	6.15
	20	0.13	<0.47	0.30	0.35	2.83
	26	0.15	<0.47	0.32	0.45	3.59
Gonio 1	0.5	0.14	<0.47	0.52	0.23	11.58
	5	0.10	<0.47	0.28	<0.09	3.27
	10	0.10	<0.47	0.21	<0.09	2.39
	20	0.11	<0.47	0.20	0.09	2.69
	25	0.16	<0.47	0.29	0.30	9.94
Gonio 2	0.5	0.15	<0.47	0.23	<0.09	12.12
	5	0.11	<0.47	0.23	0.17	3.20
	10	0.10	<0.47	0.23	<0.09	2.92
	20	0.10	<0.47	0.24	<0.09	1.32
	40	0.11	<0.47	0.22	<0.09	7.52
	48	0.13	<0.47	0.26	0.15	9.95

Phosphates. In most cases vertical distribution of phosphates are ordinary – concentration of phosphates in sea water decreasing with increasing depth and increase in content in the bottom layer because of remineralization from sediments. Only in the Poti transect stations were a bit different picture with a relatively high content of phosphates (see figure 9).

Figure 9. Concentration of phosphates in the Black sea Georgian coastal zone waters in September 2020

In a frame of the monitoring in the Black Sea Georgian coastal zone was investigated contents of some heavy metals and total petroleum hydrocarbons. Results are shown in the table (see Table 10).

Table 10. Concentrations of heavy metals and TPH in the Black Sea Georgian coastal zone monitoring stations (September 2020)

Station	Sampling Depth, m	Fe	Zn	Cu	Pb	Ni	Cr	Cd	Co	Mn	Mo	TPH, Mg/L
Gonio 1	Surface	0,0369	0,0114	0,0085	0,0051	0,0007	0,0022	0,0004	0,0003	0,0385	0,0126	0,0147
Gonio 1	20m	0,0252	0,0925	0,0177	0,0016	0,0088	0,0003	0,0001	0,0056	0,0073	0,0041	0,0517
Gonio 3	Surface	0,0086	0,0494	0,0227	0,0005	0,0012	0,0007	0,0002	0,0065	0,0225	0,0171	0,0575
Gonio 3	20m	0,0260	0,0229	0,0180	0,0007	0,0009	0,0025	0,0004	0,0551	0,0175	0,0015	0,0751
Batumi	Surface	0,0103	0,0972	0,0175	0,0016	0,0010	0,0098	0,0001	0,0056	0,0075	0,0100	0,0875
Batumi	20m	0,1184	0,0779	0,0219	0,0013	0,0007	0,0143	0,0002	0,0589	0,0167	0,0016	0,0504
Kobuleti	Surface	0,0238	0,0395	0,0684	0,0024	0,0012	0,0314	0,0003	0,0264	0,0117	0,0120	0,0971
Kobuleti	20m	0,0224	0,0166	0,0123	0,0038	0,0561	0,0444	0,0002	0,0124	0,0113	0,0115	0,0599
Poti 1	Surface	0,0136	0,0115	0,0034	0,0026	0,0203	0,0171	0,0002	0,0320	0,0048	0,0819	0,0244
Poti 1	20m	0,0189	0,0177	0,0575	0,0042	0,0008	0,0076	0,0001	0,0056	0,0165	0,0514	0,0799
Poti 2	Surface	0,0381	0,0172	0,0146	0,0003	0,0681	0,0460	0,0002	0,0331	0,0178	0,0976	0,0607
Poti 2	20m	0,0382	0,0170	0,0215	0,0034	0,0021	0,0472	0,00008	0,0333	0,0029	0,0155	0,0581
Poti 3	Surface	0,0174	0,0178	0,0063	0,0047	0,0556	0,0272	0,0002	0,0097	0,0137	0,0199	0,0746
Poti 3	20m	0,0104	0,0170	0,0354	0,0021	0,0625	0,0147	0,0001	0,0319	0,0074	0,0077	0,0275
Anaklia	Surface	0,0181	0,1001	0,0098	0,0034	0,0012	0,0097	0,0003	0,0170	0,0127	0,0250	0,0661
Anaklia	20m	0,0372	0,0137	0,0250	0,0071	0,0107	0,0313	0,0001	0,0783	0,0114	0,0436	0,0892
Chakvi	Surface	0,0222	0,0171	0,0780	0,0020	0,0007	0,0266	0,0001	0,0626	0,0207	0,0143	0,0687
Chakvi	20m	0,0242	0,0146	0,0440	0,0030	0,0231	0,0005	0,0001	0,0109	0,0181	0,0191	0,0243

Conclusions

- The obtained monitoring results indicate a prevailing high and good status for all quality elements in particular water bodies, except for the coastal water body Batumi harbour;
- The status of temperature and salinity in this water body was rated as “in normal range” which corresponds to a good status for the coastal waters (Table 9);
- The established average concentration of dissolved inorganic nitrogen indicates a high status (Table 10);
- Concentrations of orthophosphate varied in the range between high and moderate status. The established average concentration indicates a good status (Figure 9).

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